

Table 3 Summary of the most significant countries in research quality and transparency in applied linguistics research.

Rank	Country	Freq	Representative academic institution
1	United States	182	Northern Arizona University, Flagstaff, AZ
2	United Kingdom	55	University of York, York
3	China	48	Harbin Institute of Technology, Harbin
4	Japan	23	Kyoto University, Kyoto
5	Netherlands	22	Radboud University, Nijmegen
6	Canada	20	University of British Columbia, Vancouver
7	Germany	20	Max Planck Institute for Psycholinguistics, Nijmegen
8	Iran	17	Allameh Tabatabai University, Tehran
9	Australia	15	University of Melbourne, Melbourne
10	Turkey	15	Hacettepe University, Ankara